

DEBT DURDEN AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA: A CHALLENGE TO ACHIEVING SDG-8

Oluwasegun A. Adekoya^{1,2}, Esho Mary Praise³

¹Covenant University, Ota, Nigeria, ²Ardhi University, Dar Es Salaam, Tanzania,

³University of Minho, Portugal

oluwasegun.adekoyaps@stu.cu.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18049991>

Abstract

Nigeria's rising public debt threatens fiscal sustainability and the achievement of Sustainable Development Goal 8 (SDG 8). While prior studies critically examine debt-growth dynamics, few studies consider the role of labor market vulnerability and macroeconomic stability in this relationship. This study investigates the dynamic interaction between debt, debt servicing, vulnerable employment, inflation, foreign direct investment (FDI), and economic growth in Nigeria (2000-2023) using a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). Findings reveal that debt servicing hinders growth, and external debt supports growth when used efficiently. Vulnerable employment significantly influences growth, inflation has a negative effect on growth, while FDI has limited impact. The study contributes theoretically by extending debt overhang and endogenous growth frameworks to capture labor vulnerability as a growth transmission channel. This study proposes a policy action to emphasize prudent debt management and directing investment to productive sectors.

Keywords: Debt, Economic Growth, Sustainable Development Goals, Vulnerable Employment

1. INTRODUCTION

Nigeria's rising debt burden has become a central policy concern in recent years, with significant implications for sustainable growth and development. Public borrowing can, in principle, stimulate long-term growth through infrastructure investment and capital expenditure channels (Presbitero, 2012; Panizza & Presbitero, 2014). However, in Nigeria's case, the escalating cost of debt servicing has increasingly constrained fiscal space, diverting resources away from growth-enhancing sectors such as education, health, and infrastructure (IMF, 2023). In addition, recurrent expenditures including salaries, administrative costs, and non-productive consumption consume a considerable share of borrowed funds, thereby undermining the expected developmental impact of external and domestic debt (Adebayo & Omotosho, 2022).

Nigeria's growth trajectory is further complicated by structural weaknesses in its labour market, where vulnerable and informal employment dominate, accounting for more than 80% of total jobs (ILO, 2023). Coupled with persistent macroeconomic volatility particularly high inflation, fluctuating exchange rates, infrastructure shortfalls in transportation, electricity, and telecommunications, affecting productivity and efficiency and unstable foreign direct investment inflows the country faces persistent barriers to achieving inclusive and sustained economic expansion. However, investment in skill training, healthcare, social protection programs, and structural reforms can stimulate innovation and boost labor productivity (Onyekwere 2016; World

Bank, 2024; Adediran & Adekoya, 2024). These conditions directly challenge the realisation of Sustainable Development Goal 8 (SDG 8), which emphasizes sustained economic growth, productive employment, and decent work for all (United Nations, 2023).

Recent debt statistics highlight the magnitude of the challenge. Nigeria's total public debt increased from ₦12 trillion in 2015 to over ₦134.3 trillion by the second quarter of 2024, representing a more than tenfold increase within less than a decade (Debt Management Office, 2024). This steep escalation raises critical concerns regarding fiscal sustainability, debt overhang, and the crowding-out effect on private investment. As Ngoladi (2025) argues, Nigeria's position as Africa's most populous country and one of its largest economies makes the implications of its debt crisis particularly consequential, both for domestic development and regional economic stability.

Unlike much of the existing literature that treats public debt and economic growth as a linear or isolated relationship, this study introduces labor market vulnerability as a critical transmission mechanism linking debt dynamics to inclusive growth outcomes. By integrating debt overhang theory with insights from endogenous growth and labor market segmentation frameworks, the study provides a more comprehensive explanation of how rising debt and debt servicing obligations interact with informal employment structures and macroeconomic instability to shape long-run growth in Nigeria. This approach offers new empirical evidence on the structural conditions under which public debt supports or constrains progress toward SDG 8, thereby extending both the theoretical and policy relevance of the debt-growth discourse in developing economies.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of *debt burden* generally refers to the extent to which accumulated public debt and its servicing obligations constrain a country's fiscal and macroeconomic stability. It is not merely the nominal size of the debt but its relative weight against key economic indicators such as GDP, export earnings, and government revenue that determines sustainability (Krugman, 1988; Reinhart & Rogoff, 2010). In this regard, debt burden can be understood as the pressure exerted on current and future government budgets by debt servicing requirements, which may crowd out productive investment and limit the capacity for economic development (IMF, 2023). Economic growth, conceptually, is the sustained increase in a country's output of goods and services, typically measured by changes in real gross domestic product (GDP) over time. Beyond a mere quantitative increase in output, growth reflects improvements in the productive capacity of the economy, driven by factors such as capital accumulation, labour force expansion, technological progress, and institutional quality (Solow, 1956; Barro, 1991). Within the framework of sustainable development, economic growth is also linked to inclusive employment creation, productivity enhancement, and poverty reduction (World Bank, 2024; United Nations, 2023). Institutions are seen as the primary drivers of growth in a nation's economy, with other factors such as energy, human capital, and technology serving as intermediary elements (Adediran & Adekoya, 2025).

A large and growing literature explores how public debt affects macroeconomic performance. Two complementary mechanisms dominate the theoretical discussion. First, the *debt-overhang* mechanism argues that high expected future debt service reduces incentives for private and public investment because prospective returns will be taxed away to service existing obligations (Krugman, 1988; Sachs, 1989). Second, the *fiscal crowding-out* channel emphasizes that rising debt service absorbs government revenue, restricting public capital formation (infrastructure,

health, education) and thereby lowering potential growth (Pattillo, Poirson, & Ricci, 2002; Reinhart & Rogoff, 2010). These theoretical channels imply nonlinearity: moderate, well-invested borrowing can raise growth, whereas excessive or misallocated borrowing becomes contractionary (Presbitero, 2012; Panizza & Presbitero, 2014).

Ogunlana (2023) studied the external debt incurred by the Nigerian government and how it can become alarming. To fully understand the movement of external debt in Nigeria, the study analyzed the trend and commencement of past debt accumulations and why this debt was incurred in the first place. Now, the government can be the most important tool in managing the debt burden by formulating growth-friendly structural policies that focus mainly on resolving the strain of debt in Nigeria. This study lacks econometric modelling of debt-growth channels.

A country's economic health does not determine the final state of the nation; every country has a moment of economic instability before an ascent. Nigeria's economic growth and development depend on supporting policies and sound governance, this study emphasized how good governance can trigger socio-economic growth and development in Nigeria by investing time and resources into building certain sections that, in the long run, influence economic growth (Onyekwere, 2016). In the study by Ogunlana (2023), the approach suggested to reduce or eradicate debt burden was focused on the government building practical policies that guide towards a debt-free country, and both studies highlight the role of the government in the country.

Looking at past analysis and trends, Nigeria has been borrowing beyond its capacity in order to pay debt while accumulating even more debt. Employing the use of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) estimation to analyze economic stability, exchange rate, and debt load and correlation over the long period, Onyele and Nwadike, (2021) discovered that excessive borrowing has infiltrated the investment directed at funding project focused at enhancing economic growth and a proposed recommendation was for government to invest in high investment that will produce high financial return that can be used to settle the debt and build the economy. This study however focused on short-term correlation, while ignoring labor market and macro variables.

Ocholi and Isah (2024) examined the relationship between Nigeria's debt burden and sustainable growth from 2015 to 2021. The study found that debt burden, debt service payments, and exchange rate fluctuations did not significantly influence Nigeria's sustainable growth and suggested that the government invest in the natural and human resources of the country to build and generate steady revenue to even out the debt burden. A limitation stems from the limited period, which does not address long term dynamics.

Matthew and Adetayo (2022) employed the econometric technique of non-linear autoregressive distributed lag (NARDL) to analyze debt in relation to the Nigerian economy. Reducing debt service payments can boost Nigeria's short-term economic growth by removing leakages from the circular flow that hinder development. The study suggests that Nigerian monies should be allocated to invest in the country's economy and increase internal capital formation. To prevent Nigeria's economy from further deterioration, the government should empower policymakers, capable bodies, and regulatory agencies to oversee effective budget management and the use of funds. The study however, does not link to SDG 8 or employment quality.

The United Nations (2025) buttressed that promoting long-term economic growth, productive employment, and good jobs for all is critical for a sustainable future and is essential for the world's growth. Sustainable Development Goal 8 focuses on producing high-quality jobs, encouraging

entrepreneurship, and promoting inclusive economic growth. It was emphasized that the path to reaching Goal 8 confronts considerable hurdles as a result of mounting debt in developing nations like Nigeria and geopolitical crises, and these elements pose a threat to achieving economic growth.

3. METHODOLOGY

The model examines the long-run and short-run relationship existent in relation to debt burden and economic growth in Nigeria while on the run to achieve SDG 8. The data were sourced from World Development Indicators for year 2000-2023 which encompasses a period of high external borrowing. The dependent variable (GDP) was used to capture economic growth. It was further measured as a function of independent variables which are total debt service, vulnerable employment, inflation, foreign direct investment and external debt stocks. The econometric expression is written as:

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_t + \beta_2 W_t + \beta_3 L_t + \beta_4 I_t + \beta_5 A_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (3.1)$$

Where:

Y: Real Gross Domestic Product, X: Total Debt Service, W: Vulnerable Employment, L: Inflation, I: Foreign Direct Investment, A: External Debt Stocks

Vector Error Correction Model Expression

$$\Delta GDP_t = \alpha (GDP_{t-1} - \beta_1 TDS_{t-1} + \beta_2 VE_{t-1} - \beta_3 INF_{t-1} + \beta_4 FDI_{t-1} + \beta_5 EDS_{t-1} - c) + \sum_{i=1}^{p-1} \Gamma_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + u_t \quad (3.2)$$

Where: - Δ denotes first differences (short-run changes) - GDP_t = Gross Domestic Product - TDS_t = Total Debt Service - VE_t = Vulnerable Employment - INF_t = Inflation - FDI_t = Foreign Direct Investment - EDS_t = External Debt Stocks - α = speed of adjustment to long-run equilibrium - β_j = long-run cointegration coefficients - Γ_i = short-run dynamic coefficients for lagged differences - u_t = error term.

VECM is appropriate as it crucial to analyze how Nigeria's economy responds to debt shocks and macroeconomic fluctuations over time.

4. ANALYSIS

Table 1: VECM Estimates for Nigeria (2002–2023)

Variable	Long-Run Coefficient (CointEq1)	t-Statistic	Significance	Short-Run Coefficient (D(-1))	t-Statistic	Significance
GDP	1	—	—	0.826	3.36	Significant
TOTAL DEBT SERVICE	-1.28×10^{11}	-8.1	Significant	-7.42×10^8	-1.33	Not significant
VULNERABLE EMPLOYMENT	9.84×10^{10}	4.24	Significant	3.09×10^{10}	2.68	Significant
INFLATION	-8.36×10^{10}	-4.81	Significant	1.96×10^8	0.32	Not significant

FDI	1.00×10^{11}	0.77	Not significant	-1.93×10^9	-0.53	Not significant
EXTERNAL DEBT STOCKS	54.96	9.74	Significant	0.7877	1.13	Not significant
Error Correction Term D(GDP))	-0.0126	-2.15	Significant	—	—	—

Source: Authors' Computation (2025)

5. DISCUSSION

The Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) estimates reveal significant long-run relationships between debt burden, macroeconomic variables, and economic growth in Nigeria. The cointegrating equation indicates that total debt service (TDS) negatively affects GDP, implying that the burden of debt repayment diverts resources away from productive investment, constraining long-term economic growth. This aligns with findings by Ekor *et al.* (2021) and Ndubuisi (2017), who reported that debt service payments adversely affect Nigeria's economic performance.

Conversely, vulnerable employment shows a positive long-run association with GDP suggesting that growth in Nigeria is partly driven by informal or precarious employment. This is consistent with Ehikioya *et al.* (2020), who found that public debt has limited effects on formal employment creation, reflecting a structural challenge for SDG 8, which emphasizes decent work rather than growth dominated by informal labor.

Interestingly, inflation exhibits a negative long-run impact on GDP, confirming that sustained high inflation erodes real economic output, consistent with Ndubuisi (2017). Foreign direct investment (FDI) is statistically insignificant, indicating that inflows of FDI do not reliably translate into growth, possibly due to sectoral misalignment or limited spillover effects. This contrasts with Ndubuisi (2017), who found that FDI positively influences economic growth, highlighting the complexity of FDI's role in Nigeria.

Finally, external debt stocks (EDS) are positively associated with GDP, suggesting that borrowing can stimulate growth if effectively channeled into productive sectors, supporting the results of Abalaka *et al.* (2023). Collectively, these findings illustrate a nuanced debt-growth nexus in Nigeria: while servicing debt is harmful, judicious use of external borrowing can support long-term growth objectives.

The short-run dynamics reinforce these long-run findings. The error correction term (ECT) for GDP is negative and significant (ECT = -0.0126, $t = -2.15$), indicating that approximately 1.3% of deviations from long-run equilibrium are corrected annually. The slow adjustment rate suggests that the Nigerian economy responds gradually to shocks, underscoring its vulnerability to fiscal and external disturbances.

In the short run, only past GDP and vulnerable employment significantly influence current GDP, whereas debt service, FDI, inflation, and external debt stocks do not have immediate effects. This indicates that short-term growth is largely persistent and driven by historical output and informal

labor dynamics, rather than formal investment or debt shocks, echoing the observations of Ehikioya *et al.* (2020).

6. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATION

This study highlights the complex relationship between debt burden and economic growth in Nigeria, emphasizing its implications for achieving SDG 8. The findings reveal that high debt service payments negatively affect economic growth by diverting resources from productive investment, whereas external debt stocks can positively contribute to growth if efficiently channeled into productive sectors. Vulnerable employment continues to play a significant role in driving both short- and long-term GDP, while inflation constrains growth, and foreign direct investment shows limited impact. The findings present a nuanced view of Nigeria's economic structure. Positive relationships between GDP and external debt stocks, vulnerable employment, and inflation suggest that these factors may contribute to growth. Conversely, negative effects from debt service and FDI highlight structural challenges: high debt repayments may limit productive investments, while FDI may not translate efficiently into growth, reflecting potential inefficiencies in capital allocation. The contrasting results on FDI emphasize the need for further research into how foreign investment impacts economic growth in Nigeria, including considerations of sectoral alignment, policy environment, and spillover effects. Overall, the results had shed light on the importance of prudent debt management and policies that promote productive investment and formal employment to achieve SDG 8.

The findings have several theoretical and practical implications. The negative effect of debt service reinforces debt-overhang and fiscal crowding-out theories, demonstrating that high debt repayments constrain productive investment. Policymakers should therefore prioritize prudent debt management, debt restructuring, and strategic allocation of borrowed funds toward sectors that enhance long-term growth. The positive role of vulnerable employment highlights the economy's reliance on informal labour, but sustainable growth requires policies that formalize employment, improve labour productivity, and strengthen social protection, ensuring that growth is both inclusive and aligned with SDG 8. The negative impact of inflation emphasizes the need for macro-stability policies to protect real incomes and incentivize productive investment. The weak effect of FDI unveils the importance of targeted investment policies, ensuring that inflows are directed to sectors with high spill overs and linkages to domestic firms. Finally, the positive association between external debt stocks and GDP supports growth-friendly borrowing, where funds are channelled strategically to infrastructure, technology, and human capital development.

7. LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER STUDIES

Further studies could also expand the geographical scope to West Africa which could include other regional blocs in Sub-Saharan Africa, allowing for comparative analysis.

Authors Declaration: The authors declare that this study is original, plagiarism free and adheres to ethical publication standard.

Authors Contribution: Introduction and Literature Review, Mary Esho, Methodology, Analysis, Discussion of Result and Conclusion and Implication, Oluwasegun Adekoya.

Data Availability Statement: The data utilized for this study will be made available upon reasonable request.

Conflicts Of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- Arowolo, A. O., & Douglas, C. E. (2022). *Electricity generation and renewable energy policy in Nigeria: Assessing innovation drivers for cleaner energy transitions*. **American Journal of Environment and Climate**, 1(2), 42–52. <https://journals.e-palli.com/home/index.php/ajec/article/view/258>
- Adebayo, T. S., & Omotosho, T. V. (2022). External debt and economic growth in Nigeria: Evidence from a nonlinear autoregressive distributed lag approach. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 49(5), 923–942. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JES-09-2020-0455>
- Adediran, O. S., & Adekoya, O. A. (2025). Energy efficiency and institutional strength: Catalysts for Nigeria's economic expansion. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 1492, 012022. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1492/1/012022>
- Debt Management Office (DMO). (2024). *Nigeria's total public debt stock as at June 30, 2024*. Abuja: Debt Management Office. Retrieved from <https://www.dmo.gov.ng>
- International Labour Organization (ILO). (2023). *Nigeria: Decent work country diagnostics*. Geneva: International Labour Organization.
- International Monetary Fund (IMF). (2023). *Nigeria: 2023 Article IV Consultation—Staff Report*. Washington, DC: International Monetary Fund.
- Matthew, A. O., & Adetayo, A. O. (2022). Debt sustainability and economic growth in Nigeria. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 1054(1), 012053. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1054/1/012053>
- Ngoladi, U. (2025, January 14). Nigeria's national debt burden: A detailed analysis of the growth from N12 trillion in 2015 to N138 trillion in 2024. *Athena Perspectives*, 2(1). Retrieved from <https://athenacentre.org/nigerias-national-debt-burden-a-detailed-analysis-of-the-growth-from-n12-trillion-in-2015-to-n138-trillion-in-2024/>
- Ocholi, A. I., & Isah, Y. (2024). Debt burden and sustainable development in Nigeria (2015–2021). *Journal of Political Discourse*, 2(3), Article 2. Retrieved from <https://www.jopd.com.ng>
- Ogunlana, O. A. (2023, October). *Nigeria and the burden of external debt: The need for debt relief (Session 1_5-6)*. G24. Retrieved from https://g24.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/Session-1_5-6.pdf
- Onyele, K. O., & Nwadike, E. C. (2021). Impact of national debt burden on economic stability in Nigeria. *Economics and Business*, 35(1), 91–106. <https://doi.org/10.2478/eb-2021-0006>
- Onyekwere, B. A. (2016, November). Economic growth and development in Nigeria. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (Kuwait Chapter)*, 6(3). Retrieved from https://www.arabianjbm.com/pdfs/KD_VOL_6_3/4.pdf

- Panizza, U., & Presbitero, A. F. (2014). Public debt and economic growth: Is there a causal effect? *Journal of Macroeconomics*, 41, 21–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmacro.2014.03.009>
- Presbitero, A. F. (2012). Total public debt and growth in developing countries. *European Journal of Development Research*, 24(4), 606–626. <https://doi.org/10.1057/ejdr.2011.62>
- United Nations. (2023). *Sustainable Development Goals: Goal 8 – Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all*. New York: United Nations. Retrieved from <https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal8>
- United Nations. (2025). *SDG Action segment: Goal 8 – Decent work and economic growth*. United Nations. https://sdgs.un.org/sites/default/files/2025-01/SDG%20Action%20Segment%20Goal%208_1.pdf
- United Nations. (2025). *Goal 8: Economic growth – United Nations Sustainable Development*. United Nations. Retrieved from <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/economic-growth/>
- World Bank. (2024). *Nigeria economic update: Turning the corner?* Washington, DC: World Bank. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org>